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Differences in collaboration level regarding biomedical translation: application in Electroacupuncture research area¹

Jose A. Moral-Munoz^{*}, Antonio Velez-Estevez^{**}, Miguel A. Martin-Piedra^{***} and Manuel J. Cobo^{****}

^{*}joseantonio.moral@uca.es

Department of Nursing and Physiotherapy, University of Cadiz, Avda. Ana de Viya, 52, Cadiz, 11009 (Spain)

^{**}antonio.velez@uca.es

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Cadiz, Avda. De la Universidad, 10, Puerto Real, 11519 (Spain)

^{***}mmartin@uca.es

Tissue Engineering Group, University of Granada, Avda. de la Ilustración, 11, Granada, 18016 (Spain)

^{****}mjcobo@decsai.ugr.es

Department of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, University of Granada, Calle Periodista Daniel Saucedo Aranda, Granada, 18071 (Spain)

Introduction

Biomedical translation is considered as “*the process of turning observations in the laboratory, clinic and community into interventions that improve the health of individuals and the public — from diagnostics and therapeutics to medical procedures and behavioral changes*” by the National Center for Advancing Translational Science (NCATS) (Nakao, 2019). Consequently, this field is of vital importance in the present and future of the human health well-being, since it facilitates the dissemination of new therapeutic approaches (Austin, 2021).

Moreover, the National Institute of Health (NIH) substantially invest in the Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) program, considering its key focus area. The CTSA program is one of the most important initiatives in translational medical funding to date, developing a strong and growing body of influential research results (National Institutes of Health, 2022). In 2010, the UK increased the budget of the Medical Research Council (MRC), intending to enhance support for translational research (Medical Research Councils UKRI, 2022). Similarly, in 2013, the EU created the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine (EATRIS), a network of European biomedical translation hubs incorporating over eighty academic research centers (EATRIS, 2022).

In that way, there are several methods for identifying biomedical translation through bibliographical data (Padilla-Cabello et al., 2022). Translational science, such as general science, could imply the cooperation among different units, which in fact, could be placed in

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different cities or country. That is, translational science could be also developed in international collaboration scheme. In that way, international research collaboration (IRC) has grown in the last decades as the complexity of science has also augmented, and multidisciplinary teams, facilities and a big pool of resources are needed to develop complex research projects (Suresh, 2012). IRC is considered one of the keys of the shift from little science to big science, which address major topics in which advancements can have benefits around the globe (UNESCO, 2015). One example of this can be the COVID-19, in which multinational teams of researchers contributed to the understanding and development of the vaccine. However, although IRC has big benefits, institutions and nations face in the dichotomy of maintaining their competitiveness while depending on international cooperation to solve complex research projects (Chinchilla-Rodríguez, Sugimoto, & Larivière, 2019). In this research system, biomedical translation can be seen as a measure of the phases of applicability of biomedical studies, in which the patenting of research advances can increase the competitiveness of a country or group of countries (Nature, 2021). Therefore, understanding differences in the collaboration types according to the translation of studies is crucial to aid the process of strategic decisions of enterprises, institutions, and nations.

In that way, to perform the analysis presented in this study, the Electroacupuncture research area was selected. Electroacupuncture is like acupuncture, inserting needles by hand but then attaches to a device that generates electrical current that cause stimulation of the needles (Deutsch & McDonough, 2008). It is a biomedical research area in which the effects were studied in animals and its molecular mechanisms are attracting the interest of the scientific community (Tamtaji et al., 2019), so it is an adequate research area where analyses the differences in collaboration levels.

Thus, the main aim of the present study is to analyze the differences in collaboration level according to the biomedical translation using Electroacupuncture research area as set of documents. This document is structured as follows: 1) Methods, providing a description of the techniques and procedures followed to identify de collaboration levels, the biomedical translation and the statistical analysis to objectively determine the differences; 2) Results, showing the results obtained after performing the analyse; 3) Discussion, where the main implications of the obtained results are discussed, and 4) Conclusion, providing a synthesis of the main findings of our study.

Methods

Search strategy

Data was collected from PubMed with the search query “*Electroacupuncture*”[Mesh], obtaining 4,550 papers. Then, the data about translation measures were retrieved from iCite (<https://icite.od.nih.gov>), a tool to get a dashboard of bibliometrics for papers indexed in PubMed, allowing to download the results for further analysis. Then, we get the values for each paper in each category (Human, Animal or Molecular/Cellular -Mol/Cell-), according to the MeSH term assigned. The 4,550 papers were also searched in Scopus database, to enrich the metadata with the affiliations of each paper, obtaining 4,307 papers of the original corpus (94.65%).

Defining collaboration levels

The corpus was divided into three mutually exclusive sets, according to the collaboration level:

- Local: affiliations of authors were at the same organization and the same country.
- National: affiliations were in a single country but at different organizations.
- International: multiple authors from different countries participated in the papers.

The 410 papers that lacked affiliation were discarded (9.52% of 4307). Therefore, 3,897 papers of the 4550 (85.64%) originally obtained in PubMed were used in this contribution. Then, 3897 papers were divided in the collaboration levels: 2,250 papers of the 3897 were local (57.74%), 1,255 were national (32.20%) and 392 were international (10.06%).

Impact-related measures (i.e., geometric mean of citations, percentage of uncited papers, sum of citations, and percentage of total citations) were calculated to show possible differences between collaboration types, due to translational-related factors or other ones. The geometric mean was used, since the citations distribution follows a log-normal (Thelwall, 2016).

Visualization of the biomedical translation

To show the differences between the collaboration levels according to translation, we used a ternary diagram, showing the triangle of biomedicine. According to the Weber's approach (Weber, 2013), articles are classifying as Human, Animal of Molecular/Cellular, or a combination of these three categories. The categories are based on the MeSH terms assigned by the NLM indexers. Therefore, articles could have more than one of these classifications or none of them.

The triangle of biomedicine gives a quantitative way to compute if a set of papers are producing important outputs for clinical medicine and to identify translational science (Weber, 2013). In this triangle (Figure 1), papers close to the top corner are human-related, papers near the left corner are more related to molecular/cellular, and papers near to the right corner are animal related.

Figure 1. Triangle of Biomedicine. Figure modified from Figure 1 in Hutchins et al. (2019).

To construct the triangle, for each collaboration type (i.e., local, national, international), we plotted the three translational measures (human, animal, molecular/cellular), showing how many papers (in percentage to the collaboration type) were in each part of the diagram. If multiple papers were at the same point, we increased the volume of the circle representing the papers.

The conversion of the three dimensions (i.e., Human, Animal, Molecular/Cellular) in a bidimensional space was made by means of the following equations:

$$x = Animal \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - MolecularCellular \times \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$$y = Human - \frac{Animal}{2} - \frac{MolecularCellular}{2}$$

Being $(0, 1)$ the top corner (Human) of the triangle, $(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$, the right corner (Animal) $(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$, and $(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, -\frac{1}{2})$ for the left corner (Molecular/Cellular) as describe by Ian Hutchins et al. (2019).

Statistical analysis

In order to analyse the differences between collaboration levels, a statistical analysis was performed using the JASP software (JASP Team, 2022). First, an analysis of the normality was performed through the Shapiro-Wilk test. In the case of normality, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test will be used, which will be followed by Scheffe or Bonferroni's post hoc test. In case of abnormal distribution, the Kruskal-Wallis test will be used, reporting a Dunn's post hoc test to know the differences between the three collaboration levels, local-national, local-international, and national-international. The level of significance will be set at 5%.

Results

A total of 3,897 papers were finally considered in this study, following the process described above. First, Table 1 shows the distribution and citations received by the papers at each collaboration level. It is important to remark that half of the analysis corpus is produced in local collaboration and only 10.06% of the whole production is developed with international partners. Nevertheless, the impact, in terms of citations, is higher at the international level.

Table 1. Measures by collaboration type

	Local	National	International
#Papers	2,250	1,255	392
% Papers	57.74%	32.20%	10.06%
Citations (geometric mean)	5.65	8.07	14.18
% uncited papers	14.67%	15.30%	4.85%
Sum of citations	25,530	21,086	10,668
% total citations	44.56%	36.81%	18.62%

Second, we report the values of the biomedical translation for each collaboration level (Table 1) and the three ternary triangles (Figure 2) in which the values for each collaboration type in each of the categories that define de biomedical translation are represented. The volume of the spheres is related to the number of documents that are located in this area of the triangle. Furthermore, the proportion of documents is provided inside these spheres.

Table 2. Biomedical translation by collaboration type

	Local	National	International
Avg. Human	0.39	0.40	0.41
Avg. Animal	0.52	0.48	0.49
Avg. Mol/Cell	0.09	0.12	0.10

Figure 2. Biomedical triangle by collaboration level: a) local, b) national, and c) international

In that way, finally, we obtained that the three categories did not follow a normal distribution, according to the Shapiro-Wilk test, so the Kruskal-Wallis test with the Dunn's post hoc test was used to know the differences among the collaboration levels (Table 2), and between them (Table 3).

Table 3. Differences among the collaboration levels according to the different categories of the biomedicine translation

	Statistic	df	p-value
Human	0.106	2	0.949
Animal	6.716	2	0.035*
Mol/Cell	24.711	2	<0.001*
*Significant results $p < 0.05$. df: degree of freedom.			

Table 4. Differences between the collaboration levels according to the categories of the biomedicine translation

	Collaboration	z-value	p-value
Human	Local-National	0.201	0.420
	Local-International	0.295	0.384
	National-International	0.156	0.438
Animal	Local-National	2.580	0.005*
	Local-International	0.842	0.200
	National-International	-0.774	0.220
Mol/Cell	Local-National	-4.971	< 0.001*
	Local-International	-1.192	0.117
	National-International	1.900	0.029*

*Significant results $p < 0.05$.

In views of these results, there were not significant differences among collaboration levels in Human category ($H(2) = 0.106$, $p = 0.949$). Furthermore, there were no differences between collaboration level, local-national ($p = 0.420$), local-international ($p = 0.384$), and national-international ($p = 0.438$). Conversely, there were significant differences among collaboration levels in Animal category ($H(2) = 6.716$, $p = 0.035$), obtaining no differences in local-international ($p = 0.220$) and national-international ($p = 0.200$), but there was in local-national ($p = 0.005$) collaboration. Finally, the Mol/Cell category presented significant differences among collaboration levels ($H(2) = 24.711$, $p < 0.001$), with no differences in local-international ($p = 0.117$), but there was in local-national ($p < 0.001$) and national-international ($p = 0.029$) collaboration.

Discussion

After carrying out the different analyses proposed and the results presented, we can determine that there are disparities in the different collaboration levels according to the categories measured to determine biomedical translation. A total of 3,897 papers were analysed to determine the collaboration levels and biomedical translation.

Continuing with the order in which our results appear, the first finding is that articles in international collaboration have a greater impact than articles in local or international collaboration. This finding confirms what is already well known, IRC leads to an increase in scientific impact in terms of academic citation (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019). Moreover, most of the collaborations are at the local level. Although it would be necessary to make an in-depth analysis and since there are no bibliometric studies in which Electroacupuncture is studied specifically, this therapy is part of the therapies recognized as traditional Chinese medicine (Hopwood & Donnellan, 2010), over time it has been mostly studied in the People's Republic of China. Similarly, in a recently published bibliometric study (Jiang, Zhang, Li, Zhao, & Ye, 2021), authors analysed the production and collaboration in systematic reviews and meta-analysis on acupuncture, determining that the largest producer of documents in this area is the People's Republic of China. Although this study did not provide an analysis divided by different collaboration levels, it can be assumed that there is a high level of collaboration between the different research agents, since the numbers are quite high with respect to the rest of the producers.

Moreover, considering the numerical and visual results about the biomedical translation by collaboration levels, no differences were found in the Human category, although differences

were found in the Animals and Mol/Cell categories. This may be because, as stated above, Electroacupuncture is an intervention with a long tradition in traditional Chinese medicine (Hopwood & Donnellan, 2010) and has been studied primarily in humans. There are recent studies that incorporate results applied to animals, but there are still many aspects related to its effect that need to be studied from a basic research point of view (Han et al., 2021). If we consider the Animal and Mol/Cell category, differences were found in collaboration types. It is previously known that, although the growth in IRC involves all sciences, the pattern of collaboration differs according to scientific fields (Bozeman & Corley, 2004), reflecting the differences between basic and more applied sciences (Newman, 2004). Applied sciences, reflected in the Human category, are less elitist in the development of collaborative research and tend to be more dynamic and open systems (Leydesdorff, Wagner, Park, & Adams, 2013). Therefore, these dynamics in collaboration patterns could explain the differences in our findings.

Although the results shown are relevant, it should be kept in mind that there are certain limitations to the study presented. First, the limitations of the database and the methodology used. The analyses were carried out using studies obtained from the Web of Science and the iCite tool was used to determine the biomedical translation. Therefore, the results could change when using another source for the data and a different methodology. In addition, internationalization occurs through a series of multifactorial situations, so an in-depth study of the characteristics that lead to differences in the different levels of collaboration should be carried out.

Conclusion

To our knowledge this is the first study analysing the differences in collaboration levels by biomedical translation, also applied to the Electroacupuncture research field. In view of the results and the discussion reported above, we can state that international collaboration obtains a higher impact, in terms of citations, in contrast with the rest of the types of collaboration. Furthermore, although the research in Electroacupuncture is mainly focused on human research, due to its predominant clinical application, there are differences among collaboration types in animal and mol/cells applied research. Therefore, we provide a new approach to measure another dimension of the research collaboration, the biomedical translation.

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